

SOME LINGUISTIC ISSUES OF COMMUNICATIVE ASPECT OF SPEECH

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The article studies the role of lexical nominations in the events in the form of speeches, the relations between lexis and propositive nominations, and also their mutual dependence.

Key words: communicative aspect, predicative, nominatives, propositive nomination, theme, rheme.

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Words with a complete meaning or independent words can be of peculiar functional value in the structure of a sentence. Words with an incomplete meaning or non-independent words can reach only functional activity in the structure of a sentence. According to the statement of G.A. Zolotova, any surface is considered to be the object of functional activity of another smaller surface. If certain surface forms a relationship with another larger surface, it is believed to be the means of formation of that larger surface. Amenable to the view of G.A. Zolotova, syntactic means require particular materials characteristic to them. For this reason, there exists a special system of structure of syntax. On the basis of these concepts the notions of “meaning” and “function” are distinguished. Meaning implies a morphological concept, function implies a syntactic concept. This, definitely, contributes to the combination of the concept of meaning and function. [1]

Accordingly, when G.A. Zolotova analyzes topic parts of a sentence she claims that a part (theme) named with the term “datum” is indicated in accordance with the speaker’s preference, not with that of a listener, and thereby it acquires communicative activity. Furthermore, she states despite the fact that the term (rheme) “topic” obtains a logical emphasis; it is indicated in correspondence with what is significant from a semantic view point within the expression of information by a speaker, not from a logical viewpoint. She mentions that at present time a logical emphasis which is important from a communicative point of view fulfills the task of culminating point.

In our estimation, this opinion of G.A. Zolotova seems to need some elucidation. Since a communicative paradigm that defines itself with its name forms not in a language, but in speech. The scheme of this paradigm can be solely envisaged in a language. In our view, opportunities of a language exist in a virtual condition prior to communicative process. Communicative process means conversation, discussion.

In the research of John Austin there is given an idea about the following three types of pragmatic acts: locutive act, illocutive act and perlocutive act. [3] The researcher makes mention of the fact that a locutive act being associated with pronunciation of a phrase unites phonetic, factic and retic acts within its surface. Phonetic act studies the problems connected with the pronunciation of components of a phrase and a phrase itself on the basis of its phonological rules, retic act studies the issues connected with semantic features of a phrase.

As we observed, while illocutive act reveals a speaker’s goal, perlocutive act demonstrates the influence of illocutive act that is shaped in the speech of a speaker on a listener. In general, all three pragmatic act in spite of their being independent are closely

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interconnected, since all of them show activity simultaneously. This can be observed even in the process of formation of a propositive structure. To put it differently, it can be perceived that a locutive act is a speaker's colloquial style, an illocutive act is the formation of a speaker's speech (questions, answers, suspicion, belief, order, wish and etc.), a perlocutive act is the influence of a speaker's speech on who it is directed to.

When a communicative massive sentence is transposed into a phrase, it loses its communicative features. However, its nominative meaning is retained.

It is also worth mentioning that in most cases a speaker opts for a nominative meaning in its simplest form. Actually, this type of situations is mainly observed in a colloquial speech. For instance, can see a complicated formation of the following question in French in its variant given in the Russian language "Qui rest ce qui est arrive?" (Кто есть тот, кто пришёл). In this case the answer might be complicated as well: Тот, кто пришёл, есть Иван. But in a colloquial speech as simple nominative units as it is possible are chosen: Иван пришёл or Иван. [4]

Accordingly, it is viewed that there is a situation equal to referent behind a nominative meaning of a sentence. A sentence can consist of one compound (It is raining. Morning) or multiple components. However, a nominative meaning does not have an impact on its connection with a certain situation. Communicative condition is associated with the application of nominative constructions in speech. In some cases a nominative meaning serves as invariant for several transforms of a sentence, and it does not have a negative effect on the expression of a nominative meaning, but via the use of these transforms in communicative procedure it can be seen that they are differentiated: Asrora o'zining sho'xligi, og'zi botirligi bilan butun qishloqqa nom chiqargan edi (S.Ahmad.Ufq) – Asroraning o'zining sho'xligi, og'zi botirligi bilan butun qishloqqa nom chiqarganligi. (Asrora has always been famous for her joviality and bravery.)

It is apparent that a nominative meaning expressed in transforms is based on single semantic invariant. However, it is doubtless that every transform is used in a particular communicative process.

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